

AUTOMATED SPEECH SENTIMENT ANALYSIS FOR MOROCCAN DIALECT SPEAKERS USING DEEP LEARNING AND MFCC-BASED FEATURES

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Abstract

Sentiment analysis is used in several fields, such as teleconsultations in the medical field, or emergency calls to the police or firefighters. Voice analysis is used to know the emotional state of the person on the device. In our study, we propose an automated system to classify Moroccan dialect speakers' emotion using Deep Learning (DL) and voice-extracted features such as Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC). Moroccan dialect also known by the name 'Darija', is the dialect spoken by most citizens of Morocco. The Darija is very different from Arabic official dialect that we have in newspapers and TV. While previous research has predominantly focused on textual sentiment analysis using Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, our work introduces an approach by incorporating voice sentiment multiclassification for the Moroccan dialect. In our paper, we propose a voice sentiment analysis classification on a database that we created and that contains 2000 audios recorded with Moroccan dialect speakers. The proposed automated system classifies 5 different types of sentiment happy, neutral, sad, angry or fearful.

Keywords: Sentiment Analysis, Signal Processing, Deep learning, MFCC, Emotion Recognition, Arabic Dialect, Linguistics.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Moroccan Arabic dialect, also known as Darija, is the spoken dialect in the Kingdom of Morocco. It is a variety of Maghrebi Arabic, which belongs to a group of dialects spoken in the Maghreb region of North Africa. Moroccan Arabic has been significantly influenced by other languages and cultures over centuries, including French, Spanish and Portuguese [1]. While Modern Standard Arabic is utilized in formal contexts such as education, media, and government, Moroccan Arabic is the language spoken daily by most of the population. It possesses its own vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammatical features that set it apart from other Arabic dialects. It is noteworthy that the Moroccan dialect is composed, notably incorporating words from Amazigh (Berber) languages, French, and Spanish, reflecting the historical and cultural ties of the country with diverse civilizations [2].

Moroccan Arabic exhibits significant regional variations. Different areas in Morocco may display distinct phonological, lexical, and syntactic features. Researchers have explored how these variations reflect local identities and social dynamics [3]. Urban centers often experience greater linguistic diversity due to historical and contemporary factors. Conversely, rural areas may retain more traditional linguistic characteristics.

Sociolinguistic studies investigate how urbanization influences linguistic change. Sociolinguists have examined how linguistic variations in Moroccan Arabic are linked to social factors such as social class, education, and profession. Variations can be observed in vocabulary choices, pronunciation, and grammatical structures based on social stratification [4].

Sentiment analysis, a burgeoning field with applications across diverse sectors, plays a pivotal role in understanding human emotions and attitudes. In contexts such as teleconsultations and telepsychiatry in the medical field and emergency calls, the ability to gauge the emotional state of individuals is crucial. Voice analysis, a key component in this endeavor, provides valuable insights into the nuances of human expression.

In response to the growing importance of sentiment analysis, particularly in linguistically distinct regions, our study focuses on the Moroccan dialect, commonly known as 'Darija'.

While existing research predominantly leans towards textual sentiment analysis through NLP techniques, our work is based on voice sentiment analysis for the Moroccan dialect. In [5], authors proposed a lexicon-based sentiment analysis approach with NLP of Algerian Darija, which is very close to The Moroccan Darija, they got an accuracy of 79.13%. In [6], researchers classified 10 Arabic digits from speech in Tunisian and Moroccan dialects, using Support Vector Machine (SVM), they resulted in 97.5% of recognition rate.

In [7], authors used Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), Naive Bayes classifier, and SVM, to classify a dataset of Facebook comments in Tunisian dialect, the results showed an error rate of 23% with SVM for example. In [8], authors developed a tool using NLP to annotate Moroccan Darija text dataset with a precision of 97.2%. In [9], authors used neural networks, Support Vector Machine and decision trees in Matlab and Praat software, to recognize emotion from Moroccan broadcasts from YouTube.

This paper outlines our proposal for an automated system employing Residual Neural Network (RNN) model and voice-extracted features, such as MFCC, to classify Moroccan dialect speakers based on their emotional states. The creation of a comprehensive database, encompassing 2000 audio recordings of Moroccan dialect speakers, serves as the foundation for our analysis. By classifying sentiments into five distinct categories—happy, neutral, sad, angry, or fearful—we aim to contribute to the evolving landscape of sentiment analysis, shedding light on the emotional intricacies of the Moroccan dialect and showcasing the efficacy of voice-based approaches in linguistic analysis.

2. METHOD

2.1 Dataset Information

The database used for deep learning of the model contains 2000 vocal signals, labelled, and classified on 5 types of emotion. The database created is one of the largest databases of labelled recordings of the Moroccan Arabic dialect with several emotions, currently available in Morocco.

To create our database, we first started by developing the script to record. We did a search and writing workshop on the words, phrases, and terms most used by Moroccans on a daily basis. As a result, 150 sentences were written with respect for proportionality in relation to the 5 emotions to be classified, therefore 30 sentences for each type of emotion. Then, we filtered the sentences to retain only 5 for each type of emotion, based on the terms and words most used in the Moroccan dialect 'Darija'. We ended up with 25 sentences in total. The table below lists the terms used for registration and their classification.

Table 1: List of recorded sentences and their classification

N°	Sentence in Moroccan Dialect	Emotion Class
1	Chokran bezaf ! Rabi ykhalik	Happy
2	Khebar zwina hadi	Happy
3	Labass hamdolillah	Happy
4	Wa mebrouk älik !	Happy
5	Äejebni bezaf film	Happy
6	salam o älikom labass	Neutral
7	Jib mäak hadak leketab	Neutral
8	Ana f benhmed daba	Neutral
9	Cheta tahet lyoum	Neutral
10	match meläoub f donor	Neutral
11	Wellahi ta dalmoni	Sad
12	Wellahi ma ana	Sad
13	Beka fiya meskin	Sad
14	Äyit bezaf	Sad
15	La hawla wala kowata ila bilah	Sad
16	Chno had chi derti !	Angry
17	Sebahato lilah !	Angry
18	Yalah ! kheroj äliya !	Angry
19	Chno had lebessala !	Angry
20	Chno had kalat adab !	Angry
21	Nari ! Ach hadchi !	Fearful
22	Naari Kahelnaha !	Fearful
23	Eh ! Khelaätini !	Fearful
24	Eh ! Bism allah arahman rahim !	Fearful
25	La ! La ! äafak La !	Fearful

2.2 Dataset Distribution

The database used for testing contains 2000 records. It was built after we recorded the voices of 80 people, 40 women and 40 men. Each person was recorded in 5 different states of emotion, I quote: happy, neutral, sad, angry, or fearful. Each speaker had to read 25 scriptures in Moroccan dialect, 5 for each type of feeling. The recording took place in a local radio studio, in a soundproof room. The total recording of the 25 sentences per person has an average duration of 1.32 minutes. Audios are sampled at 44 KHz and exported under the .wav extension. The table 2 below shows the distribution of the speakers by age groups: Child, Adolescents, Youth, Adults and seniors.

Table 2: Speakers' distribution by groups of age

N°	Group	age	Number of records
1	Child	6 – 13	500
2	Adolescents	14 - 18	500
3	Youth	19 - 30	500
4	Adults & Seniors	31 -73	500

The ages of those registered range from 6 years to 73 years, with an average age of 25 years. The shortest full recording of the 25 sentences is 49 seconds long and the longest recording is 88 seconds long. The average duration of one sentence recording is 3 seconds.

2.3 Dataset Processing

After getting the 80 records, we started the signal processing step. Each recording is processed to deduce 25 .wav type signals, each 5 corresponding to a type of classification. For audio processing, we used Audacity (v.3.2.5), software used for recording and editing digital audio sources.

Table 3: Labeling of emotion classes

N°	Emotion class label	Emotion
1	n	Neutral
2	h	Happy
3	a	Angry
4	s	Sad
5	f	Fearful

We were able to recover 2000 signals. Then, we began the stage of labeling and classification of the data collected. The signals of each recorded person are grouped, named, and classified according to the following nomenclature: **rc N _ G C N'**, with

- rc: for recording (record).
- N: for the number of the original recording (80 in total).
- G: for the gender of the person, m for Male or f for Female.
- C: for the emotion class {n, h, a, s, f}.
- N': for the registration number per class (5 in total).

The label 'rc' for record + original recording number + m or f for 'Male' or 'Female' + the emotion class + recording number by class.

Table 4: Labeling of speakers' gender

N°	Speaker Gender label	Gender
1	m	Male
2	F	Female

The matrix below gives an example of the labeling of the 25 records of a person with the record number 25 and gender male. For technical reasons linked to deep learning processing with Python code, and to facilitate the reading of the signals, the numbering of the signals starts from 0 and goes up to 4 (we start counting from 0 instead of from 1), instead of 1 to 5, for the 5 emotion classes.

Table 5: Matrix of the labeling of recordings for person no. 25 of the male type

N°	Neutral	happy	Angry	Sad	Fearful
1	rc24_mn0	rc24_mh0	rc24_ma0	rc24_ms0	rc24_mf0
2	rc24_mn1	rc24_mh1	rc24_ma1	rc24_ms1	rc24_mf1
3	rc24_mn2	rc24_mh2	rc24_ma2	rc24_ms2	rc24_mf2
4	rc24_mn3	rc24_mh3	rc24_ma3	rc24_ms3	rc24_mf3
5	rc24_mn4	rc24_mh4	rc24_ma4	rc24_ms4	rc24_mf4

Sound is a wave vibration, an analog signal that has frequency and amplitude. Frequency is the number of vibrations per second. The higher the frequency, the higher the pitch. The amplitude corresponds to the height of the wave. When the volume of the sound is high, the amplitude will also be high, as can be seen in Figure 1 below, where we have an image of the audio signal for a person saying a happy statement "Chokran bezaf, Rabi ykhalik" which we can translate in English to "Thanks a lot, May God bless/save you". The audio lasts 1,5 seconds. On the X axis, we have time, and on the Y axis, we have amplitude.

Figure 1: Audio wave for a happy statement speech

Below we have an image of the Mel spectrogram of the same audio in figure 2. The frequency is between 0 and 19KHz. The x axis is for time and the y axis is for frequency. The colors on the spectrogram represent the energy or the power of a frequency in the audio frame at giving time t. A significant presence of colors means the person is speaking [10]. On the contrary, if there are no colors in a frame of the signal (presence of black color) means there is blank and the person is not speaking, as we can see in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Mel spectrogram for the same audio.

We are using Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) to capture the spectral characteristics of the speech signal which are well-suited for representing the distinctive features of speech sounds [11]. We start by framing our signal to frames between 20 and 40ms. For every segment of the signal, we compute the power spectrum to identify the frequencies present in that portion. The power spectrum, once determined, undergoes processing through a Mel scale filter bank. This bank isolates frequency bands in a manner that mirrors the way human ears perceive sound through vocal tract. Afterward, log filter banks are applied, followed by the application of short-term Fourier transform (STFT) coefficients (Equation 1) [12]. This step compresses the information from the filter banks, resulting in the generation of MFCCs.

$$STFT\{x[n]\}(m, \omega) \equiv X(m, \omega) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x[n]\omega[n - m]e^{-j\omega n} \quad (1)$$

One of the main advantages of the Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCC), is that it quantifies the gross-shapes of an audio spectrum which helps in vowel identification for example. Another important advantage is that it removes the fine spectral structure which is often less important and does not contain relevant information. The coefficients of MFC will describe some characteristics of a part of the sound.

First coefficients of MFCC (usually the first 12) keep the most important information of the signal like: formants, spectral envelope, on the other side, the higher coefficients contain information about the glottal pulse, which we are not interested in. The most relevant features are the formants and the spectral envelope which represent the vocal tract.

Beside MFCC, we extracted The Harmonics-to-Noise Ratio (HNR). HNR measures the balance between harmonic components (which are multiples of the fundamental frequency) and non-harmonic or noise components in a speech signal [13]. In the context of voice analysis, HNR is often used to evaluate the quality of the voice signal. A higher HNR generally indicates a clearer and more harmonic-rich voice, while a lower HNR may suggest the presence of noise or other distortions in the signal.

$$HNR = 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{Harmonic Energy}}{\text{Noise Energy}} \right) \quad (2)$$

As we can see in the equation 2 above, HNR is calculated by comparing the energy or power of the harmonic components to the energy or power of the noise components. The ratio of harmonic energy to noise energy is often expressed in decibels (dB) and is the HNR.

We also used The Jitter and shimmer features. These terms are associated with the

analysis of speech signals and are used to quantify variations in pitch and amplitude, respectively. These measures are often used in the field of speech pathology and voice analysis. Jitter and shimmer, as sonic attributes in vocal signals, originate from irregular oscillations of the vocal folds, leading to perceived traits such as coarseness, breathiness, or huskiness in a speaker's voice. Although every natural speech inherently displays a certain extent of jitter and shimmer, assessing these features functions as a widespread approach for detecting vocal pathologies. Diverse elements, such as individual behaviors like smoking or alcohol intake, have the potential to raise levels of jitter and shimmer in the voice [14]. Furthermore, aspects like voice volume, language, and gender can also exert an impact on these sonic characteristics.

Jitter refers to the short-term frequency variations in the pitch of the speech signal. It is essentially a measure of the cycle-to-cycle variability in pitch. Jitter is often used to assess the stability or regularity of vocal fold vibrations. Deviations from a regular pattern may be indicative of voice disorders. Jitter is typically calculated as the percentage variation in the pitch period of consecutive speech cycles (Equation 3). A common measure is jitter percent, which represents the average percentage variation in pitch period.

Figure 3: Jitter and Shimmer measures in voice signal.

Shimmer quantifies the short-term amplitude variations in the speech signal. It measures the cycle-to-cycle variations in the amplitude of the speech signal, indicating the instability of the vocal fold vibrations. Shimmer is used to assess the stability or regularity of the amplitude of the speech signal. Like jitter, increased shimmer values may indicate voice disorders. Shimmer is often expressed as a percentage and is calculated as the average percentage variation in amplitude from one cycle to the next (Equation 4).

Let F be the instantaneous frequency at time t , and be the amplitude at time t . Then, jitter and shimmer can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Jitter} = \frac{1}{N-1} * \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \left| \frac{F_0(t_{i+1}) - F_0(t_i)}{F_0(t_i)} \right| \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Shimmer} = \frac{1}{N-1} * \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \left| \frac{A(t_{i+1}) - A(t_i)}{A(t_i)} \right| \quad (4)$$

In these formulas, N is the number of samples or cycles in the analyzed speech segment. These formulas provide a quantitative measure of the short-term variations in pitch (jitter) and amplitude (shimmer) in the speech signal.

Another feature we extract from the records, is Zero-Crossing rate (ZCR). ZCR measure is used in signal processing, particularly in the analysis of audio signals to measure the rate at which a signal changes its sign, or more precisely, the rate at which it crosses the zero axis. In the context of audio signals, the zero-crossing rate can provide information about the frequency content and temporal characteristics of the signal related to voicing and speech articulation, such as pitch or the presence of certain phonemes in speech and can also reflect the rapidity of changes in the sign of a signal.

Vowels typically have a smoother and periodic waveform, resulting in a lower ZCR. The rate of zero-crossings in vowel sounds tends to be lower compared to consonant sounds. Consonants often involve more rapid changes in the speech signal, leading to a higher ZCR [15]. Plosive and fricative consonants, which involve quick bursts of energy, can contribute to higher zero-crossing rates.

The zero-crossing rate is calculated by counting the number of times a signal crosses the zero axis within a specified time window. Mathematically, it can be expressed as:

$$\text{ZCR} = \frac{1}{N-1} * \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} |\text{sign}(x_i) - \text{sign}(x_{i-1})| \quad (5)$$

Where:

- N is the number of samples in the signal.
- x_i is the i -th sample of the signal.
- $\text{sign}(\cdot)$ is the signum function, which returns -1 for negative values, 0 for zero, and 1 for positive values.

We also used the fundamental frequency (F_0) feature, often referred to as pitch. F_0 is the perceived frequency of the fundamental harmonic in the vocal source. In simpler terms, it represents the rate at which the vocal folds vibrate during speech production.

The fundamental frequency is a critical perceptual aspect of speech and is closely related to the perceived pitch of a speaker's voice.

F_0 can contribute to distinguishing between different speakers. Individuals often have characteristic pitch ranges, and changes in pitch can be used as a feature for speaker identification. Variations in F_0 are associated with emotional expressiveness in speech.

For example, a higher pitch may be linked to excitement or stress, while a lower pitch may convey calmness or sadness. Different languages and dialects may exhibit distinct pitch patterns. Analyzing F0 can provide insights into linguistic and regional variations in speech.

F0 is a primary cue for perceiving gender in speech. On average, males tend to have lower F0 values than females and children. The typical F0 range for adult males might be around 85 to 180 Hz, while for adult females, it could be around 165 to 255 Hz.

Another extracted feature we worked with is the Root Mean Square (RMS). It provides a measure of the energy content or amplitude of a speech signal. It is particularly useful for quantifying the overall intensity or loudness of the signal. Deviations in loudness may be indicative of certain voice disorders or changes in the vocal mechanism.

Loudness variations in speech can also be valuable in assessing signal quality, speech disorders or guiding speech therapy by quantifying changes in vocal intensity.

The RMS value of a signal is calculated by taking the square root of the mean of the squared values of the signal samples over a specified time window. Mathematically, for a discrete signal $x[n]$ with N samples:

$$RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} * \sum_{n=1}^N x[n]^2} \quad (6)$$

The signal samples $x[n]$ corresponds to the amplitude values of the speech waveform at each time point. The RMS value provides a representation of the signal's energy, and it is calculated over short frames or windows to capture the dynamic variations in loudness.

2.4 Processing and Model Architecture

To classify the emotions in the signals extracted from audio recordings, we decided to develop a deep learning model based on ResNet 152. The network has 152 layers. The key innovation in ResNet architectures is the use of residual learning, where shortcut connections or skipped, connections are introduced to skip one or more layers [16]. This helps solve the vanishing gradient problem and allows the training of very deep neural networks.

ResNet-152 is particularly known for its high depth, making it suitable for complex tasks such as image and voice recognition, object detection and segmentation. The model inputs are the coefficients and metrics calculated in the preprocessing step, the Mel-scale cepstral coefficients (MFCC), the metrics HNR, ZCR, F0, RMS and other calculated statistical measures of a speech signal like Mean, Variance and Standard Deviation. The output of our learning model is the prediction of the emotion class of the speaker in a given recording.

Figure 4: Preprocessing and Model training architecture

The data cleaning, pre-processing, and the model development were done using Python language (v.3.11.3) and the library Pytorch. For the training, we used a Lenovo ThinkPad E16, Intel Core i5-7300U, CPU 2.60 GHz 2.71 GHz 16 Go RAM.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed deep learning model based on ResNet152 gives a high accuracy of 0,901 for the classification of the test dataset [17]. Accuracy metric represents the ratio of the number of the correct predictions to the total number of dataset samples. In Table 6 below we have the different accuracy rates for the 5 classes of speaker's emotion.

Table 6: Accuracy Metric results for the 5 classes of emotion

Neutral	happy	Angry	Sad	Fearful
0,895	0,882	0,891	0,931	0,907

In the past few years, many papers worked on the textual sentiment analysis using techniques like NLP. In our work, we propose a voice sentiment recognition classification on a database that we created and that contains 2000 audios recorded with Moroccan Arabic dialect speakers.

Few works did a multi-classification of 5 types of emotion in Arabic dialect, with large number of speakers. In our study, we did the classification of 5 emotions from. The dataset we constructed is one of the largest databases of speech emotion recognition available in Morocco. We also used MFCC, and other statistical measures calculated from the signals. The classification gave us high score of accuracy, 89.5% for the happy emotion, 88.2% for the neutral speech, 89.1% for the sad emotion, 93.1% for the angry emotion and 90.7% for the fearful emotion.

4. CONCLUSION

In our paper, we proposed a Moroccan Arabic dialect speech sentiment analysis for 5 different emotions, using the MFCC coefficients and other measures extracted from the processed speaker's speech signals. After trying different deep learning models, we choose RNN model ResNet152 for the training. The results of the model multi-classification show an accuracy of 90.12%. Our findings demonstrate the potential of employing voice sentiment analysis in understanding the emotional nuances within the Moroccan dialect. The integration of Deep Learning and MFCC- based features proves to be effective in achieving accurate sentiment classification, paving the way for advancements in voice-based emotional analysis for diverse linguistic contexts. This research contributes to the expanding landscape of sentiment analysis, emphasizing the significance of voice- based approaches in linguistically distinct regions such as Morocco and North Africa.

Data and Software Availability Statements

The Dataset used in this work is available on <https://dx.doi.org/10.21227/ev21-c430> .

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